

Polarographic Study of the Influence of Concentration and Nature of the Different Supporting Electrolytes on the Kinetics of the Irreversible Electrode Reactions of Ga(III) and Ge(IV)

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The polarographic behaviour of Ga(III) and Ge(IV) has been studied at 25° in the presence of varying concentrations (0.05–1.0M) of different supporting electrolytes, viz., NaNO₃, NaClO₄, NaCl, KCl, KNO₃, NH₄Cl, NH₄NO₃, Ba(NO₃)₂, Sr(NO₃)₂, Ca(NO₃)₂, Mg(NO₃)₂ and Al(NO₃)₃. The reduction of both the depolarizers at d.m.e. has been found to be diffusion-controlled and irreversible. Koutecky's treatment has been applied to calculate the rate constant ($k_{f,h}$) at various potentials along the course of a polarogram in the presence of different supporting electrolytes. The values of the kinetic parameters (αn_a and $k_{f,h}^0$) have been calculated as a function of the concentration of supporting electrolyte. Conclusions regarding the extent of irreversibility drawn from these parameters are found to be in conformity with each other.

In a previous publication¹, the influence of temperature on the kinetics of the irreversible electrode reactions of Ga(III) and Ge(IV) has been reported. In another publication² we have studied the influence of aqueous mixtures of ethane-1,2 and propane-1,2-diols on the electrode reaction of Ge(IV). A survey of literature reveals that a polarographic study of the influence of the concentration and nature of different supporting electrolytes on the kinetics of the electrode reactions of Ga(III) and Ge(IV) has not been undertaken so far. The present study has therefore been undertaken to determine the polarographic characteristics and kinetic parameters in the presence of varying concentrations of different supporting electrolytes.

Experimental

Standard solutions of Ga(NO₃)₃·2H₂O (Fluka, AR), GeO₂ (Fluka, AR) and of supporting electrolytes (AR, BDH) were prepared in conductivity water by direct weighing. The concentration of each of the depolarizers in the final solution to be polarographed was maintained at $1.0 \times 10^{-3}M$. The polarograms of the solutions at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$ were obtained by using a manual polarograph (Toshniwal CL02) in conjunction with polyflex galvanometer (Toshniwal PL 50); Purified nitrogen was used for removing the dissolved oxygen. The potentials were measured against a saturated calomel electrode (S.C.E). Triton X-100 ($1 \times 10^{-3}\%$) was used as the maxima suppressor. The pH of the solutions was measured by using Philips pH-meter (PR 9404) and kept constant at 6.2 by adding a very dilute solution of HCl or KOH. The number of electrons (n) involved in the electro-reduction of each depolarizer was determined by millicoulometric method³

and was found to be 3 for Ga(III) and 4 for Ge(IV). Knowing the value of n , the diffusion coefficient (D) of the depolarizers was calculated by Ilkovic equation at different concentrations of the supporting electrolytes. The potential-dependent rate constant, $k_{f,h}$ has been calculated at different concentrations of the supporting electrolytes by Koutecky's treatment^{4,5}. The kinetic parameters (αn_a and $k_{f,h}^0$) have been obtained from log $k_{f,h}$ vs $E_{d.s.}$ plots. Throughout the measurements the current at the end of the drop (i.e., the maximum current) was recorded for the reasons given by Meites^{6(c)}. The d.m.e. had the following characteristics (in 0.1M NaClO₄, open circuit): for Ga(III), $m = 1.87$ mg/sec; $t = 3.1$ sec; $m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 1.84$ mg^{2/3} sec^{-1/2}; $h_{0.077} = 72.2$ cm and for Ge(IV), $m = 3.59$ mg/sec; $t = 3.2$ sec; $m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 2.84$ mg^{2/3} sec^{-1/2}; $h_{0.077} = 72.2$ cm.

Results and Discussion

Both Ga(III) and Ge(IV) yield a single well-defined wave in the presence of increasing concentrations of different supporting electrolytes. However, in the case of nitrates of NH₄⁺, Ba²⁺, Sr²⁺, Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺ and Al³⁺ the waves become drawn out at higher concentrations of these salts.

The reduction of both the depolarizers is diffusion-controlled as is shown by the linearity of i_d versus $h_{0.077}^{1/2}$ plots. The various criteria^{6(a)-8} of irreversibility indicate that the electrode reactions of Ga(III) and Ge(IV) are irreversible.

Influence of the concentration and nature of supporting electrolytes on the kinetics of the irreversible

TABLE 1—INFLUENCE OF INCREASING CONCENTRATIONS OF SUPPORTING ELECTROLYTES ON THE POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS AND KINETIC PARAMETERS ($\alpha_{0.6}$ AND $k_{f,h}^0$) OF THE ELECTRODE REACTIONS OF Ga(III) AND Ge(IV)

Conc. of supporting electrolyte M	i_d μA	$-E_{1/2}$ vs (S.C.E.)	Slope mV	$D \times 10^5$ cm^2/sec	$\alpha_{0.6}$	$k_{f,h}^0$ cm/sec
Ga(III)						
NaNO ₃						
0.05	10.47	1.11	130	7.19	0.42	6.24×10^{-10}
0.10	9.95	1.12	140	6.48	0.39	3.46×10^{-10}
0.20	9.76	1.12	143	6.25	0.38	1.62×10^{-10}
1.00	6.56	1.12	170	2.82	0.32	8.63×10^{-11}
NaClO ₄						
0.05	10.64	1.11	140	7.44	0.39	2.36×10^{-9}
0.10	10.29	1.12	143	6.95	0.38	8.42×10^{-10}
0.20	9.22	1.13	148	5.58	0.36	6.24×10^{-10}
1.00	7.81	1.14	170	4.00	0.32	3.16×10^{-10}
NaCl						
0.05	11.71	1.11	140	9.00	0.39	2.62×10^{-9}
0.10	10.29	1.11	143	6.95	0.38	9.04×10^{-10}
0.20	9.58	1.12	146	6.02	0.37	7.63×10^{-10}
1.00	8.29	1.14	165	4.50	0.33	3.07×10^{-10}
KCl						
0.05	10.03	1.12	130	6.60	0.42	7.12×10^{-10}
0.10	8.98	1.13	135	5.29	0.40	4.63×10^{-10}
0.20	8.18	1.14	137	4.39	0.36	3.02×10^{-10}
1.00	7.92	1.15	142	4.11	0.35	8.43×10^{-11}
KNO ₃						
0.05	10.21	1.06	145	6.84	0.37	8.22×10^{-9}
0.10	9.33	1.08	148	5.71	0.36	6.31×10^{-9}
0.20	8.09	1.09	150	4.30	0.36	3.14×10^{-9}
1.00	6.69	1.09	153	2.94	0.35	7.26×10^{-9}
NH ₄ Cl						
0.05	12.77	1.08	100	10.71	0.54	2.84×10^{-11}
0.10	9.93	1.12	135	6.46	0.41	4.06×10^{-11}
0.20	9.58	1.14	160	6.02	0.34	6.07×10^{-11}
1.00	6.39	1.16	162	2.68	0.33	3.21×10^{-11}

(Contd. Table)

(Contd. Table from 1)

Conc. of supporting electrolyte <i>M</i>	i_d μA	$-E_{i/2}$ vs (S.C.E.)	Slope mV	$D \times 10^6$ cm^2/sec	αn_d	$k_{f,h}^0$ cm/sec
Ga(III)						
NH₄NO₃						
0.05	10.64	1.11	105	7.44	0.52	3.07×10^{-11}
0.10	10.64	1.12	120	7.44	0.45	7.02×10^{-11}
0.20	9.58	1.12	135	6.02	0.40	1.24×10^{-11}
1.00	Wave drawn out					
Ba(NO₃)₂						
0.05	12.67	1.14	100	10.54	0.54	7.62×10^{-11}
0.10	12.49	1.14	135	10.25	0.46	4.04×10^{-11}
0.20	12.14	1.14	170	9.68	0.32	2.26×10^{-10}
1.00	Wave drawn out					
Sr(NO₃)₂						
0.05	8.98	1.11	130	5.29	0.42	6.61×10^{-10}
0.10	8.09	1.12	150	4.28	0.36	3.27×10^{-9}
0.20	Wave drawn out					
Ca(NO₃)₂						
0.05	10.56	1.11	140	7.32	0.39	2.46×10^{-9}
0.10	8.00	1.11	160	4.30	0.34	7.02×10^{-9}
0.20	Wave drawn out					
Mg(NO₃)₂						
0.05	14.19	1.12	140	13.22	0.39	2.82×10^{-9}
0.10	12.77	1.12	143	10.71	0.38	9.06×10^{-9}
0.20	10.11	1.12	145	6.71	0.37	7.04×10^{-9}
1.00	Wave drawn out					
Al(NO₃)₃						
0.05	10.64	1.08	110	7.44	0.49	1.22×11^{-10}
0.10	8.87	1.10	130	5.16	0.41	9.31×10^{-10}
0.20	Wave drawn out					
Ge(IV)						
NaClO₄						
0.05	23.42	1.42	160	8.49	0.34	2.27×10^{-10}
0.10	23.06	1.42	155	8.24	0.33	4.02×10^{-10}
0.20	21.64	1.40	175	7.25	0.31	9.62×10^{-11}
1.00	14.01	1.30	200	3.04	0.27	8.12×10^{-11}

(Contd. Table)

(Contd. Table from 1)

Conc. of supporting electrolyte M	i_d μA	$-E_{1/2}$ vs (S.C.E.)	Slope mV	$D \times 10^6$ cm^2/sec	αn_a	$k_{f,h}^0$ cm/sec
Ge(VI)						
NaCl						
0.05	25.19	1.40	145	9.83	0.37	5.46×10^{-11}
0.10	24.48	1.38	140	9.28	0.36	8.14×10^{-11}
0.20	23.06	1.36	170	8.24	0.32	8.62×10^{-10}
1.00	20.93	1.34	155	6.79	0.31	3.14×10^{-10}
KCl						
0.05	25.19	1.44	150	9.83	0.36	5.42×10^{-11}
0.10	24.48	1.44	160	9.28	0.34	8.46×10^{-11}
0.20	21.64	1.40	200	7.26	0.27	3.12×10^{-10}
1.00	21.29	1.37	200	7.02	0.27	8.64×10^{-10}
NH ₄ NO ₃						
0.05	20.22	1.32	55	6.39	0.98	8.62×10^{-15}
0.10	18.44	1.30	80	5.26	0.68	4.90×10^{-15}
0.20	12.06	1.29	85	2.25	0.64	7.04×10^{-15}
1.00	Wave drawn out					
Ba(NO ₃) ₂						
0.05	26.66	1.28	130	11.01	0.42	8.64×10^{-14}
0.10	Wave drawn out					
Sr(NO ₃) ₂						
0.05	14.54	1.27	90	3.27	0.60	4.34×10^{-14}
0.10	14.90	1.24	90	3.44	0.60	8.12×10^{-14}
0.20	Wave drawn out					
Ca(NO ₃) ₂						
0.05	16.32	1.27	110	4.13	0.49	4.87×10^{-14}
0.10	Wave drawn out					
Mg(NO ₃) ₂						
0.05	12.59	1.27	90	2.45	0.60	2.02×10^{-15}
0.10	12.95	1.26	80	2.59	0.58	9.62×10^{-15}
0.20	Wave drawn out					

electrode reactions of Ga(III) and Ge(IV) :

(a) Electrode reaction of Ga(III) :

Table 1 includes the values of αn_a and $k_{f,h}^0$ as a function of the concentration of different supporting

electrolytes. The influence of the concentration of the supporting electrolytes on the kinetics of the irreversible electrode reaction of Ga(III) is discussed below in terms of the values of the kinetic parameters :

(i) αn_a values :

From Table 1 it is evident that the product αn_a decreases with increasing concentrations of all the supporting electrolytes. According to Meites^(1d) the value of α may, in principle, vary from nearly 0 to nearly 1; in many cases it is not far from 0.5. Both adsorption and neglect of double layer structures, however, may have appreciable effects, and a few values of α below 0.1 or above 0.9 have been reported. The value of n_a must obviously be integral, and in most cases it is probably 1. Though it is generally believed that only a single electron can be transferred at a time during the course of an electrode reaction, a value of n_a exceeding 1 would not necessarily mean that two or more electrons are actually added simultaneously, but merely that the successive steps are too nearly simultaneous to be distinguished on the time scale implicit in a polarographic measurement.

The fact that αn_a values lie in the range 0.30-0.50, and in the light of the arguments of Meites as mentioned in the preceding para, an attempt to estimate n_a apparently leads to a conclusion that $n_a = 1$. As already mentioned, αn_a decreases with an increase in the concentration of all the supporting electrolytes. Since the decrease in αn_a values is indiscrete and at no stage the two consecutive values vary by an integral factor > 1 , the possibility of a decrease in the value of the product αn_a due to a change in n_a may be ruled out. Thus, it can be safely concluded that it is α which is decreasing. α signifies^o the fraction of the applied voltage which favours the cathodic reaction, $\text{Ga}^{3+} + 3e \rightarrow \text{Ga}$. A decrease in the value of ' α ' thus implies that the transfer of electrons is made increasingly difficult. In other words the electrode reaction of Ga(III) is rendered increasingly more irreversible with the increase in the concentration of the supporting electrolytes. A negative shift in $E_{1/2}$ values (Table 1) supports this conclusion.

(ii) $k'_{f,h}$ values :

A perusal of Table 1 reveals that these is no regularity in the variation of $k'_{f,h}$ with increasing concentrations of the supporting electrolytes. Meites^(1b) has hinted at the limitation of $k'_{f,h}$ in interpreting the results. However, the influence of the change of concentration of the supporting electrolytes on the rate of the electrode reaction of Ga(III) can be studied¹⁰⁻¹² in terms of the value of the potential-independent rate constant ($k_{f,h}$) at a suitable potential which should be such as to lie between the potentials corresponding to the foot and the top of the polarographic wave. At such a potential both the rate of electron transfer and the diffusion determine the magnitude of the current^o. In the present system this potential has been taken as -1.14 v_s (S.C.E.) and the values of $k_{f,h}$ at this potential have been listed in Table 2. A perusal of this table shows that $k_{f,h}$ decreases with increasing concentrations of supporting electrolytes. From this, it follows that the electrode reaction of Ga(III) is rendered more irreversible with increasing concentrations of these supporting electrolytes. These

TABLE 2—VALUES OF $k_{f,h}$ AT A SELECTED POTENTIAL FOR THE IRREVERSIBLE ELECTRODE REACTIONS OF Ga(II) AND Ge(IV).

Supporting electrolyte	[Supporting electrolyte] <i>M</i>	$k_{f,h} \times 10^4$ (cm/sec)	
		Ga(III) at -1.14 vs (S.C.E.)	Ge(IV) at -1.40 vs (S. C. E.)
NaClO ₄	0.05	19.5	18.4
	0.10	18.0	16.9
	0.20	13.8	16.3
	1.00	4.5	12.4
NaNO ₃	0.05	20.1	—
	0.10	19.1	—
	0.20	12.9	—
	1.00	10.0	—
NaCl	0.05	21.3	26.4
	0.10	12.8	19.4
	0.20	9.4	19.1
	1.00	4.9	16.4
KCl	0.05	12.3	13.0
	0.10	11.3	9.4
	0.20	8.2	9.0
	1.00	6.8	8.7
KNO ₃	0.05	28.3	—
	0.10	19.4	—
	0.20	14.0	—
	1.00	10.6	—
NH ₄ Cl	0.05	39.3	—
	0.10	13.2	—
	0.20	9.7	—
	1.00	5.1	—
NH ₄ NO ₃	0.05	22.4	—
	0.10	19.6	—
	0.20	15.2	—
	1.00	—	—
Ba(NO ₃) ₂	0.05	19.8	—
	0.10	12.6	—
	0.20	9.2	—
Sr(NO ₃) ₂	0.05	17.8	—
	0.10	12.5	—
Ca(NO ₃) ₂	0.05	15.0	—
	0.10	9.3	—
Mg(NO ₃) ₂	0.05	22.1	—
	0.10	20.9	—
	0.20	18.5	—
Al(NO ₃) ₃	0.05	25.9	—
	0.10	24.8	—

conclusions are in harmony with those arrived at on the basis of the variation in αn_a values.

The influence of the nature of the cations and the anions constituting the supporting electrolytes, on the kinetics of the electrode reaction of Ga(III) has been studied by comparing the value of $k_{f,h}$ (at -1.14 vs S.C.E.) at a certain concentration (0.1 *M*) of the supporting electrolytes. The order of the $k_{f,h}$ value is as follows :

For cations (as nitrates) :

For anions (as sodium salts) :

(b) *Electrode reaction of Ge(IV) :*

Table 1 includes the values of αn_a and $k_{f,h}^0$ as a function of the concentration of the different supporting electrolytes. A perusal of this table shows that αn_a decreases with an increase in the concentration of the supporting electrolytes. Extending the same arguments as put forward in the case of the electrode reaction of Ga(III), it is inferred that the electrode reaction of Ge(IV) is rendered more irreversible with increasing concentrations of the supporting electrolytes.

The values of $k_{f,h}^0$ for the electrode reaction of Ge(IV) do not show any gradation with the increase in the concentration of the supporting electrolytes. As already discussed, in view of this limitation of $k_{f,h}^0$ in interpreting the results, the influence of increasing concentrations of the supporting electrolytes on the kinetics of the electrode reaction of Ge(IV) can be studied in terms of the values of $k_{f,h}$ at a suitable potential which has been chosen as -1.40 vs (S.C.E.). The values have been presented in Table 2. From these values it is clear that $k_{f,h}$ decreases with increasing concentrations of the supporting electrolytes thereby suggesting that the electrode reaction of Ge(IV) tends to become more irreversible with the increase in the concentration of different supporting electrolytes. This conclusion is in harmony with that arrived at on the basis of the variations in αn_a values.

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